

Non-Traditional Forms and Methods of Teaching in Primary School Lessons

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Annotation: In the article, the lesson is considered as a form of learning organization. The art of conducting lessons largely depends on the teacher's understanding and fulfillment of social and pedagogical requirements, which are determined by the tasks of the school, patterns and principles of learning. An important condition for conducting a lesson is a competent selection of methods and means of conducting a lesson. The leading role of the lesson among other forms of learning is explained by the fact that it is the most appropriate form from a scientific and pedagogical point of view, that the lesson concentrates the main part of the teacher's work with students in order for them to assimilate a system of knowledge, skills and abilities, that this is the most convenient form for systematic courses of subject curricula.

Keywords: process, principles, art, regularity, interpretation, characteristics, educational material.

INTRODUCTION

A lesson is the main organizational form of learning at school. It is not only an important organizational, but also, above all, a pedagogical unit of the learning and upbringing process, its morality, as well as the basic principles, methods and means of teaching receive real concretization and find their correct solution and are implemented only during and through the lesson. Each lesson makes its own specific, unique contribution to solving problems. The lesson performs a specific function, in which a certain part of the larger blocks of educational material finds expression.

METHODOLOGY

Formation of the objectives of the article. The purpose of the article is to reveal the possibilities of non-traditional forms and methods of teaching

The lesson as a form of educational organization has firmly taken its place in school as the main organizational form of education. A good lesson is not an easy matter. The art of conducting lessons largely depends on the teacher's understanding and fulfillment of social and pedagogical requirements, which are determined by the tasks of the school, patterns and principles of learning. An important condition for conducting a lesson is a competent selection of methods and means of conducting a lesson. On the one hand, the basis for the characterization of the lesson is a functional approach, on the other hand, it is emphasized that the functions of the lesson are determined by the laws of the learning process, the development of the student's personality, without which the goals of the lesson are unattainable. The lesson was interpreted as «pedagogical work», «complex phenomenon» characterized «integrity», «internal interaction of the parts, common logic in the activities of the teacher and class», «has the unity of educational and methodical means of influencing the mind and the soul of the child» acting for

them «critical» form of the process of knowing the world and develop their spiritual life. The theoretical idea was that the lesson acquired the ability to be flexible and diverse in the ways of organizing students, that it was not limited to equipping students with knowledge, but included the education of independence, inquisitive and creative attitude to learning, etc. [1,5].

The leading role of the lesson among other forms of learning was explained by the fact that it is the most appropriate form from a scientific and pedagogical point of view, that the lesson concentrates the main part of the teacher's work with students in order for them to assimilate a system of knowledge, skills and abilities, that it is the most convenient form for systematic courses of subject curricula.

The characteristic features of the lesson as an element of the classroom system were highlighted: a) the presence of a class with an unchanging composition of students; b) a precisely defined time; c) a firm schedule in compliance with a rational and systematic alternation of academic disciplines; d) the use of various methods to achieve didactic tasks.

Along with the external signs, the essential characteristics of the lesson were also revealed. Already at the beginning of the period, the lesson was considered as a structure-forming component of the educational process and a kind of "mirror" reflecting all aspects of school life (educational, methodical, and organizational).

Today, more and more attention is being paid to a person as a person — his consciousness, spirituality, culture, morality, as well as highly developed intelligence and intellectual potential. Accordingly, there is no doubt about the extreme importance and urgent need for such training of the younger generation, in which educated intellectual personalities with knowledge of the basics of sciences, general culture, skills to think independently and flexibly, to proactively and creatively solve life and professional issues would graduate from high school [2,8].

Non-traditional forms of the lesson are implemented, as a rule, after studying a topic or several topics, performing the functions of a teacher performing the functions of a training control. Such lessons take place in an unusual, non-traditional setting. Such a change of the usual environment is advisable, because it creates an atmosphere of celebration when summarizing the work done, removes the mental barrier that arises in traditional conditions due to fear of making a mistake. Non-traditional forms of the lesson are carried out with the obligatory participation of all students of the class, and are also implemented with the indispensable use of auditory and visual aids. In such lessons, it is possible to achieve a variety of methodological, pedagogical and psychological goals, which can be summarized as follows: students' knowledge, skills and abilities on a specific topic are monitored; a business, working atmosphere is provided, students' serious attitude to the lesson is provided; a minimum teacher's participation in the lesson is provided.

RESULTS

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the obtained scientific results.

The analysis of pedagogical literature allows us to identify several dozen types of non-traditional lessons. Their names give some idea of the goals, objectives, and methods of conducting such classes. Let's list the most common types of non-traditional lessons: The lesson is a journey. The lesson is conducted in the form of an imaginary journey. The stages of the lesson are a stop along the way. The instructor of the lesson can be a teacher or a trained student. Students are offered an itinerary, according to which they determine the position of the studied landscape. Then the children choose transport, equipment, clothes — everything they need for the trip. The lesson is structured in the form of practical research, work with visual aids, conversations and reports on natural objects "encountered" at stops during the trip.

The lesson is a fairy tale. This type of non-traditional lesson is conducted in grades 1-2 when generalizing and systematizing any seasonal topic: Summer, Autumn, Winter, Spring. As in any fairy tale, such a lesson should have positive characters (Zimushka-winter, an old Man, an ecologist, any animal or bird) and negative characters (an evil cold wind, Baba Yaga). There should be a tie in the fairy tale: a problematic

issue, an unusual situation (for example: the cuckoo's voice is heard in the winter garden), a riddle, the appearance of the hero of the fairy tale in an unusual costume. This is followed by the climax, the development of the plot, where the struggle of good and evil is obligatory, unusual new information about the heroes of the fairy tale, arguments, jokes, overcoming difficulties, etc. During this lesson, children imperceptibly answer the teacher's questions about the past material, learn new additional material on the topic of the lesson. The lesson ends with a fairy tale ending, the victory of good over evil, knowledge over ignorance, the teacher names the best experts in nature, puts marks, awards prizes. KVN lesson. It is held in the form of competitions between teams. The stages of the lesson are tasks for teams: warm-up, a practical task, a duel of captains, physical training sessions, each team chooses the name of the team captain at the beginning of the lesson. The questions and tasks in terms of content are cognitive, educational and problematic in nature, and in form they can be entertaining, humorous, playful. The quiz lesson. The lesson is similar to the KVN lesson, the only difference is that the student does not work in teams, but individually.

The quiz lesson and the KVN lesson are conducted in order to repeat the educational material.

The lesson is a game. Named a lesson may be conducted in the form of games, «a», «Wonderland», «TIC-TAC-toe» and others. The educational task of these lessons is to generalize the systematization of students. The first two games are held by analogy with the TV shows of the same name.

The lesson is an expedition. The class is equipping an expedition to Greenland. It is clear to everyone: we must prepare seriously. A list of literature is given where you can find out the history of the island, why it has such a name, and under what conditions the expedition will take place. Then the navigator sets the course for the ship. It proves which side and why it is more convenient to swim to the island. The biologist of the expedition selects material about the flora and fauna of the island, the ethnographer — about the indigenous population, their way of life, customs. There are sailors, a captain, and, of course, geographers in this expedition [4,9].

The lesson is an excursion. Nowadays, when relations between different countries and peoples are developing more and more widely, familiarity with Russian national culture is becoming an essential element of the learning process. The student should be able to conduct a city tour, talk about the identity of Russian culture, etc. The principle of dialogue of cultures involves the use of cultural material about his native country, which allows to develop the culture of representing his native country. The peculiarity of the lesson-excursion is that the learning process is realized not in the classroom, but in nature, during the direct perception of its objects and phenomena by students [3,7].

Video lesson. The use of the video also helps to develop various aspects of students' mental activity, and, above all, attention and memory. While watching in the classroom, an atmosphere of joint cognitive activity arises. Under these conditions, even an inattentive student becomes attentive. In order to understand the content of the film, students need to make some efforts. Thus, involuntary attention turns into voluntary attention, its intensity affects the process of memorization.

CONCLUSIONS

Conclusions on the topic "Non-traditional forms and methods of teaching in primary school lessons. In general, the use of non-traditional methods and forms of education in primary school not only increases children's interest in the educational process, but also contributes to the comprehensive development of their personality, including cognitive, emotional and social aspects. The use of various channels of information (auditory, visual, motor perception) has a positive effect on the strength of the impression of educational material. Thus, the psychological features of the impact of educational videos on students contribute to the intensification of the educational process and create favorable conditions for the formation of students' communicative competence [6.10].

An unconventional lesson is an organic combination of education, development and upbringing. Children like non-traditional lessons because they are creative and unusual, and most importantly— effective. But you should not conduct non-traditional lessons too often, because they will become traditional and the

level of effectiveness will decrease. In recent years, interest in non-traditional primary school education has significantly increased. This is due to the social transformations taking place in our country, which have created certain conditions for restructuring processes in the field of education — the creation of new types of schools, the active introduction into practice of various pedagogical innovations, author's programs and textbooks. The organization of non-traditional developmental education involves the creation of conditions for students to master the techniques of mental activity. Mastering them not only provides a new level of assimilation, but also gives significant shifts in mental development.

Having mastered these techniques, students become more independent in solving various educational tasks, they can rationally build their activities for the assimilation of new knowledge.

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